

ON A FRICTION MECHANISM *

IN COMPOSITE FRACTURE

Richard W. McLay
Professor
Mechanical Engineering
University of Vermont
Burlington, Vermont

Michael C. Murphy
Assistant Professor
Engineering and Technology
Norwich University
Northfield, Vermont

Abstract

The friction mechanism between the fiber and matrix that increases the apparent fracture energy is explored using a finite element analysis of a simplified planar composite. The analysis is based on the production of entropy and assumes that the linear fracture problem can be perturbed by the addition of a work term from the friction force at the fiber/matrix interface. An optimization method is proposed.

Introduction

Composite materials have become advantageous in many high-technology areas because they offer the option of choosing specifications in weight, stiffness and toughness. When dealing with the fracture of a composite, however, we find a very complex process. In particular, the toughness of a composite is enhanced by the formation of lateral cracks extending away from the primary crack, the so-called Cook-Gordon mechanism (1). But this of course compromises the ultimate strength of the structure, reduces the structural stiffness as the crack pattern ages, and influences the fatigue strength of the composite. However, without this mechanism we obtain an extremely brittle composite because the primary crack then propagates with little resistance through the entire structure, essentially resisted only by the fracture energy of the matrix, which is usually quite small in composites composed of brittle materials. The mechanism is reviewed in detail in the recent papers by Kanninen, Rybicki and Brinson (2) and McGarry, Mandell and Wang (3), where the several contributing factors in composite fracture toughness are discussed relative to the recent literature.

A primary factor in the apparent fracture energy of a composite is the friction between the fiber and the matrix (4), (5). This is seen to be important since the primary crack, propagating through the matrix, debonds the

* Work performed under the auspices of the United States Air Force Office of Scientific Research. Contract AF44620-76-C0012.

fibers from the matrix, but is resisted by the fiber pull-out as the crack opens. The energy dissipated in the friction between the fibers and the matrix as the pull-out occurs then figures into the fracture energy of the primary crack in a very complex series of motions of the structure. It is also heavily influenced by the initial deformations of the matrix as it is cured during the fabrication process. If this friction effect is linearized and combined with all other effects in the fracture energy of the interfaces of the composite, it is possible to write closed-form expressions for the crack pattern produced from the Cook-Gordon mechanism (6). However, when the effect of friction at the interface is included in its most general form, the crack pattern equations become integral expressions over a time-like variable interval. This complicates the formulation and rules out all of the usual min-max search techniques which are so useful for defining the crack pattern (6). As we shall see shortly, though, for a class of problems in which the frictional stresses at the interface are small relative to those tractions produced by the external loads, it is possible to evaluate the increase in the apparent fracture energy by perturbing the linear solution. It is the objective of this paper to explore the effects of interface friction for a simplified model based on the linear composite examined previously (6). This will be done using the finite element method with a planar composite model.

The Entropy Concept

It is well-known that the maximization of entropy controls the crackpath in the fracture of an isotropic material (7),(8). Since the composite exhibits a complex crack pattern it is necessary to extend the entropy concepts to include not only the rate of energy release but also the rate of energy dissipation (6). This is best illustrated by using the abstract concept of an entropy machine, a device in the fracture process that creates entropy. The entropy machines controlling the fracture in a composite are shown in Figure 1, where a machine is associated with the crack tip at each fracture site. In the operation of these machines it is assumed that as the crack

Fig. 1 - Entropy Machines at the Various Composite Crack-Tips

pattern spreads an increment of distance, each machine extracts energy isentropically from the strain field surrounding its associated crack-tip. The machine then converts this strain energy into internal energy in the form of heat by whatever dissipative mechanisms it has available. The heat is then

transferred away from the machine through an infinitesimal temperature gradient, i.e. isentropically. The production of entropy then occurs only in the machines, which allows us to study the production of entropy closely by using a process that is quasi-reversible (9). This is done through the use of the Clausius-Duhem inequality (10) to obtain the rate of entropy expression

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{1}{\theta_0} \left[- \frac{dU}{dt} - (\text{Dissipative rates}) \right] \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

where θ_0 is the absolute temperature of the system and U is the strain energy.

Let us assume for the analysis here that the composite is constructed of brittle, elastic materials. We will also assume that the only dissipative effects are those characterized by the fracture energy of the matrix, G_{Mat} , the fracture energy of the fiber/matrix interfaces, G_{Int} , and the friction between the fibers and the matrix once debonding has taken place. We will further assume that the process is quasi-reversible and quasi-static and in so doing neglect the kinetic energy; the resulting formulation is then in agreement with the quasi-static fracture processes in (7), (11), ---, (15). Finally, we assume that the frictional stresses between the fibers and the matrix are small constants, τ_i , with respect to those stresses associated with the boundary-value problem. This then borrows liberally from the original work of Cottrell (16) in the simplified model for friction assumed at the interfaces. With these assumptions then it is possible to compute the strain energy for the linear problem neglecting the effects of friction, but include these effects in the final computation for the effective fracture energy of the matrix. In effect, the assumptions produce a quasi-linear formulation for the composite fracture problem including the effects of friction at the fiber/matrix interfaces.

With the above assumptions the rate of entropy expression for a planar composite is found from equation (1) above as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{1}{\theta_0} \left[- \frac{\partial U}{\partial a} \frac{da}{dt} - \sum_i \frac{\partial U}{\partial a_{l_i}} \frac{da_{l_i}}{dt} - G_{Mat} \frac{da}{dt} \right. \\ \left. - \sum_i G_{Int} \frac{da_{l_i}}{dt} - \sum_i \tau_i \int \frac{d\Delta v_i}{dt} ds \right] \geq 0, \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

where a is the primary crack length, a_{l_i} are the lateral crack lengths along the fiber/matrix interfaces, and the frictional dissipation is computed by integrals of the products of the frictional stresses and the differences in the tangential displacements, Δv_i , along the respective interfaces. In keeping with the assumption of quasireversibility, we note that the bracketed term in equation (2) must be a positive infinitesimal, since it is really a statement of the first law of thermodynamics.

When a process goes toward equilibrium, the entropy will go to a maximum, in this case a maximum infinitesimal. A sufficient condition for this is that dS/dt be a maximum in the time interval $(0, \infty)$. But, because of the assumptions above it is possible to integrate equation (2) over $(0, t)$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_0(S - S_0) = - U(a, a_{l_i}) + U(0) - G_{Mat} a - \sum_i G_{Int} a_{l_i} \\ - \sum_i \tau_i \int \Delta v_i ds \geq 0, \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where $S - S_0$ is the difference between the final and initial entropy states, $U(a, a_{1i})$ is the value of the strain energy at time t and $U(0)$ symbolizes the corresponding value at time zero.

Let us define the crack pattern that maximizes the entropy as $\bar{a}, \bar{a}_{1i}, \bar{\Delta v}_i$. These values are associated with time t . Since the entropy is maximized an inequality is derived naturally from equation (3) by comparing the value of $S - S_0$ for $\bar{a}, \bar{a}_{1i}, \bar{\Delta v}_i$ with that for $a, a_{1i}, \Delta v_i$, i.e. for all crack patterns in the neighborhood of the one maximizing the entropy. But the value of the initial strain energy is common to all crack patterns. Thus, the inequality becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 -U(\bar{a}, \bar{a}_{1i}) - G_{\text{Mat}} \bar{a} - \sum_i G_{\text{Int}} \bar{a}_{1i} - \sum_i \tau_i \int \bar{\Delta v}_i ds &\geq \\
 -U(a, a_{1i}) - G_{\text{Mat}} a - \sum_i G_{\text{Int}} a_{1i} - \sum_i \tau_i \int \Delta v_i ds &, \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

where \bar{a} appears on both sides of equation (4), acting as a time-like variable. This inequality implies the theorem

Of all the crack patterns in a planar composite with $|\tau_i| \ll |\sigma_{ij}|$ (frictional stresses much less than the stresses produced by the boundary-value problem), the one minimizing

$$U(\bar{a}, a_{1i}) + \sum_i G_{\text{Int}} a_{1i} + \sum_i \tau_i \int \Delta v_i ds$$

subject to the constraint

$$-\frac{\partial U}{\partial a} = G_{\text{Mat}} + \sum_i \tau_i \int \frac{\partial \Delta v_i}{\partial a} ds$$

maximizes the system entropy.

This theorem will be used next to evaluate the effects of the interface friction on the crack pattern and the apparent fracture energy. Note that the constraint in the theorem supplies the value of the apparent fracture energy as it is influenced by the interface friction on the right-hand side of the expression.

A Composite Boundary-Value Problem

In order to gain numerical insight into the frictional mechanism we examine the boundary-value problem shown in Figure 2. This planar composite

Fig. 2 - The Boundary-Value Problem

model has symmetry conditions on the left and lower boundaries, implying that the region shown is one quadrant of a composite with two symmetrically placed fibers. The primary crack, of length a , is seen to have propagated from the lower left corner across the matrix, passing the fiber, to the position as labeled. There is assumed to be one lateral crack, of length a_l , which has propagated along the fiber/matrix interface to the length as shown. A displacement boundary condition exists on the top boundary, providing the initial strain energy needed for the crack pattern study. Our objective will be to use the finite element method to evaluate the functional in the theorem for this boundary-value problem to study the effect of the addition of friction to the problem.

We begin by performing the finite element analysis with a mesh of constant strain triangular elements, seven mesh widths high by thirteen mesh widths wide. The only mesh refinement used is directly adjacent to each crack tip or reentrant corner on the region. Adjacent to each of these points we progressively refine the mesh by a factor of 1/2 to mesh widths of 1/2, 1/4, and 1/8 of the original mesh dimension. The material properties are respectively $E = 400,000$ PSI and $\nu = .3$ for the matrix and $E = 10 \times 10^6$ PSI and $\nu = .3$ for the fiber. A unit thickness is assumed for all computations. The displacement boundary condition is specified at unity for the problem. All analyses are then referenced to the values obtained from this original computation with a constant c . That is, the values of all physical quantities are corrected by the constant c except for the value of the energy, which is corrected by c^2 .

The addition of friction to the boundary-value problem introduces a non-linearity for values of interface shear large enough to cause a change in the apparent fracture energy. Thus, any values we obtain from this analysis will be found by a sequence of successive approximations. Our objective, as in all approximate analyses, is to obtain insight with a limited set of tools that are available to us.

By computing the strain energy, U , for primary crack lengths of 15 and 20 inches with lateral crack lengths of 15, 20 and 25 inches, it is possible to obtain simple expressions for the variations of U with the lateral crack length, referenced to $a_l = 15$ inches:

$$U|_{a=15 \text{ in}} = 16639.94 - 107.875 \left(\frac{a_l-15}{5}\right) + 8.855 \left(\frac{a_l-15}{5}\right)^2 ,$$

$$U|_{a=20 \text{ in}} = 16485.71 - 108.53 \left(\frac{a_l-15}{5}\right) + 8.840 \left(\frac{a_l-15}{5}\right)^2 .$$

If we approximate the constraint expression in the theorem by a difference equation, it is possible to approximately determine c

$$-c^2 \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a} = \frac{G_{Mat}}{2} + \tau c \int \frac{\Delta(\Delta v)}{\Delta a} ds ,$$

$$c = \frac{-\tau \int \frac{\Delta(\Delta v)}{\Delta a} ds \pm \sqrt{\left(\tau \int \frac{\Delta(\Delta v)}{\Delta a} ds\right)^2 - 4 \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a} \frac{G_{Mat}}{2}}}{2 \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a}} , \quad (5)$$

where $G_{Mat}/2$ appears due to the symmetry condition of the lower boundary. For a value of $a_l = 15$ inches, the expression in equation (5) becomes

$$c = 1.495 \times 10^{-5} \tau \pm \sqrt{2.233 \times 10^{-10} \tau^2 + .0162 G_{Mat}} , \quad (6)$$

which satisfies the constraint in the theorem.

Let us now evaluate approximately the functional in the theorem for a lateral crack length $a_1 = 15$ inches. We designate this functional as I

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &= c^2 U + G_{Int} + \tau c \int \Delta v \, ds \quad , \\
 &= c^2 \left(16639.94 - 107.875 \left(\frac{a_1 - 15}{5} \right) + 8.855 \left(\frac{a_1 - 15}{5} \right)^2 \right) \\
 &\quad + G_{Int} a_1 + \tau c \left(3.526 \left(\frac{a_1 - 15}{5} \right) + 6.103362 \right) \quad . \quad (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

We have approximated the expression for the friction as a linear function. Note that c appears in equation (7) as a constant to be determined from equation (6), dependent on both τ and G_{Mat} . But the functional I now contains a single parameter, the lateral crack length. Thus, it is reduced to a classical min-max problem in calculus, resulting in

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dI}{da_1} &= c^2 \left(- \frac{107.875}{5} + \frac{8.855}{25} (a_1 - 15) \right) \\
 &\quad + G_{Int} + \tau c \left(\frac{3.526}{5} \right) = 0. \quad (8)
 \end{aligned}$$

This gives an approximate expression for the lateral crack length

$$a_1 = 75.93 - 2.823 \frac{G_{Int}}{c^2} - 1.991 \frac{\tau}{c} \quad . \quad (9)$$

Because these expressions are all obtained for expansions around $a_1 = 15$ in and a between 15 and 20 inches, it is important to recognize that they are only valid there. Thus, this constrains the values of G_{Mat} , G_{Int} , and τ appearing in equations (6) and (9) to those yielding a_1 in the range indicated. Table 1 shows the results of a trial analysis in which $G_{Int} = 1$, $G_{Mat} = 10$.

Table 1. A Trial Analysis

τ	c	$\tau/\sigma_{Boundary}$	a_1
0	.402	0	56.47
1	.402	1/2170	53.51
2	.402	2/2170	48.56
3	.402	3/2170	43.60
4	.402	4/2170	38.65
5	.402	5/2170	33.70
6	.402	6/2170	28.75
7	.402	7/2170	23.79
8	.402	8/2170	18.84
9	.402	9/2170	13.89
10	.402	10/2170	8.93

In this table the fiber/matrix interface shear stress appears in the first column. The calculated value of c appears in the second column, in this case insensitive to the values of τ in the range given. The ratio of the interface shear to the value of the normal stress generated at the boundary by the displacement boundary condition, i.e. σ_v , appears in the third column. The last column contains the computed value of the lateral crack length versus the given value of τ . The equations in this case are valid for an interface shear stress of between 8 and 9 PSI. The increase in the apparent fracture energy of the matrix for these values is negligible.

Conclusions

The friction mechanism between the fiber and the matrix that increases the apparent fracture energy has been explored using the finite element method. The technique used to determine the crack pattern in the composite is based on the production of entropy. It uses the theorem as stated and comes naturally from the inequality of equation (4). The constraint in the theorem provides a method for evaluating the apparent fracture energy of the matrix when friction effects are accounted for. While the method assumes that the friction effects are small with respect to stresses produced by the boundary-value problem, it can be extended to include friction effects which are large enough to influence the strain energy. Thus, in a sense the method is more general than first proposed here.

An optimization problem results naturally from the analyses carried out for using the theorem stated. It appears that we should pose the problem by stating it as follows:

Of all the composite configurations satisfying the weight, stiffness, and other constraints imposed, the one maximizing the apparent fracture energy of the matrix for a given crack, will maximize

$$\sum_i \int \tau_i \frac{\partial \Delta v_i}{\partial a} ds$$

for the crack.

It appears that the important parameters in such an optimization problem are the quantity stated and the ultimate strength of the fibers used. For, if we are to develop the toughness for the composite we must have available the proper materials in the fibers to do so. This is of course in agreement with a great many previous works.

References

1. Cook, J. and Gordon, J.E., "A Mechanism for the Control of Crack Propagation in Brittle Composites," Proc. Roy. Soc., Series A, Vol. 282, 1964, pp. 508-520.
2. Kanninen, M.F., Rybicki, E.F., and Brinson, H.F., "A Critical Look at Current Applications of Fracture Mechanics to the Failure of Fibre-Reinforced Composites," Composites, January 1977, pp. 17-22.
3. McGarry, F.J., Mandell, J.F. and Wang, S.S., "Fracture of Fiber Reinforced Composites," Polymer Engineering and Science, Vol.16, No. 9, September 1976, pp. 609-614.
4. Kelly, A., "Interface Effects and the Work of Fracture of a Fibrous Composite," Proc. Roy. Soc. Lond., Series A, Vol. 319, 1970, pp. 95-116.
5. Atkins, A.G., "Intermittent Bonding for High Toughness/High Strength Composites," Journal Materials Science, Vol. 10, 1975, pp. 819-832.
6. McLay, R.W., "Analysis of Fracture in a Linear Composite," Keynote Lecture on Composites, International Conference on Numerical Methods in Fracture Mechanics, Swansea, Wales, January 9-13, 1978.
7. Gurney, C. and Hunt, J., "Quasi-Static Crack Propagation," Proc. Roy. Soc. London, Series A, Vol. 299, 1967, pp. 508-524.

8. Lawn, B.R. and Wilshaw, T.R., Fracture of Brittle Solids, Cambridge University Press, New York, 1975, p. 66.
9. Fosdick, R.L. and Serrin, J., "Global Properties of Continuum Thermodynamic Processes," Arch. Rational Mechanics and Analysis, Vol. 55, 1975, pp.97-109.
10. Malvern, L.E., Introduction to the Mechanics of a Continuous Medium, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1969, pp.255.
11. Roesler, F.C., "Brittle Fractures Near Equilibrium," Proc. Phys. Soc., B69, 1956, pp.981-992.
12. Benbow, J.J., "Cone Cracks in Fused Silica," Proc. Phys. Soc., Vol. 75, 1960, pp. 697-699.
13. Cherepanov, G.P., "Crack Propagation in Continuous Media," Jour. Struct. of Solids, PMM, Vol. 31, 1967, pp. 476-488.
14. Cherepanov, G.P., "Cracks in Solids," Int. Jour. Solids and Structures, Vol. 4, 1968, pp. 811-831.
15. Evans, A.G., "Slow Crack Growth in Brittle Materials under Dynamic Loading Conditions," Int. J. Fract., Vol. 10, No. 2, 1974, pp. 251-259.
16. Cottrell, A.H., "Strong Solids," Proc. Roy. Soc., Series A., Vol. 282, 1964, p.2.

SESSION 4:
ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS
AND STRUCTURES-I

CHAIRMAN:

S. Tsai
Air Force Materials Laboratory/MBM
Wright Patterson AFB
Ohio 45433

CO-CHAIRMAN:

T.T. Chiao
Fiber Composites & Mechanics
Lawrence Livermore Laboratory (L-338)
University of California, Box 808
Livermore CA 94550

